

CONSUMER PURCHASE BEHAVIOUR ON AIR CONDITIONER – A STUDY IN VANIYAMBADI TALUK TIRUPATTUR DISTRICT TAMILNADU

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Abstract

Consumer Buying Behavior refers to consumers' actions taken (both on and offline) before buying a product or service. This process may include consulting search engines, engaging with social media posts, or various other actions. It is valuable for businesses to understand this process because it helps companies better tailor their marketing initiatives to the marketing efforts that have successfully influenced consumers to buy in the past. In this study, a research investigation was carried out to determine consumer purchase behavior towards purchasing Air conditioners in Vaniyambadi Taluk. Totally 200 consumers were selected from Vaniyambadi Taluk. The deliberate Sampling Method was adopted all through the research.

Keywords: Consumer Behaviour, Air Conditioner, Impact of consumer behavior

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Consumer Behaviour

Consumer behaviour is much more than buying things; It additionally embraces and examines approximately confidence through particular (or no longer having) matters to influence our lives and how our possessions impact the way we experience HY approximately ourselves and roughly every other our kingdom of being. In addition to knowledge, because human beings' purchase matters, we also admire how products, offerings, and intake sports contribute to the broader social global we experience. Whether shopping, cooking, cleaning, gambling, soccer or hockey, mendacity at the beach, emailing or texting friends, or maybe searching at ourselves withinside the mirror, our lives are touched through the advertising and marketing system. The area of purchaser behaviour is young, dynamic, and in flux. It is continuously being cross-fertilized through views from many unique disciplines. We have attempted to specify the area's spectacular variety in this text.

1.2 Consumer Buying Behaviour

Consumer buying behaviour is the study of buying and disposing of goods, services, ideas, or experiences by individuals, groups, and organizations to satisfy their needs and wants. Buyer behaviour has been defined as “a process, which through inputs and their use through process and actions leads to the satisfaction of needs and wants.” Consumer buying behaviour has numerous factors as a part of it that are believed to have some level of effect on the customers' purchasing decisions.

1.3 Objective of the Study

To delve into Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour that helps identify the right product choice.

1.4 Statement of Problem

There are many issues concerning Consumer Buying Behaviour while buying any product. Consumer Buying Behaviour matters when a consumer goes for purchases of products. Sellers do not sell the commodities according to the whims and fancies of consumers; instead, they dispose of the products according to their specifications resulting in consumer dissatisfaction. Channel of Distribution is sometimes wrongly selected by the sellers, and those platforms do not convey the product adequately to the consumers. Dealers are not able to fix the prices being demanded by consumers. They sell the commodities over and above the organized prices, hamper consumer buying behavior.

1.5 Importance of the Study

This study seems to be as prominent as possible as consumer buying behavior influences the purchase of products from time to time. It brings opportunities and challenges to any size of business organizations. Business Concerns also can understand what consumers want and offer the commodities as per their tastes and preferences. Consumers switch to other products due to perceived usefulness and ease of use. Producers these days make the products after incorporating the real-time needs of consumers.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study of Consumer Buying Behaviour improves the overall performance of the organization. Organisations in general increase perceived benefits of products as is in the case of competitors' products. The effectiveness of products is improved better than ever before, and consumer research is done very frequently. Organizations reduce the negative impact of products. Consumers are at their liberty while choosing the product. The volume of sales potentially increases after assuming consumer buying behavior is essential.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sharma, Ghanshyam, and Kaur, Dr. Avjeet, (2020), in their research, said that studies make explicitly a specialty of the impact of emblem name photographs and ads on the consumer is shopping for behavior in the direction of electronic merchandise (Air

Conditioner, Inverters, and Microwave ovens). Similarly, those proposed works examine the elements that can affect the emblem photo and ads and ultimately affect consumer shopping for behavior. The reasons for selecting digital merchandise (Air Conditioner, Inverters, and Microwave ovens) are because of the growing choice of consumers closer to this merchandise. The examiner might assist the readers in understanding the client buying behavior in unique to electronic merchandise like Air Conditioner, Microwave ovens, and inverters, supported which the policymakers or advisors of the organizations could make suitable techniques to promote the goods and emblem status quo for the duration of a higher way in the competitive environment.

Raju (2020) reveals that consumer behavior is defined by selecting, buying, utilizing, and disposing goods and services through humans or establishments to fulfill their desires. organizations need to understand the numerous factors that have touched on purchasers to create purchases. Those factors could also be reference businesses, cultural factors, and economic elements and alike; additionally, they need to understand the purchase system that is going into making purchase choices with the assistance of customers to obtain both rural and concrete markets. The rural markets provide an extensive choice of opportunities way to their incredible length and modifications that have taken vicinity over the years. A vital quit could also be drawn from the research because consumers' buying behavior is essential for agencies. While it's also seen that rural and concrete customers need to be segmented nicely so on derive sales and make the most of the markets. This research paper offers an overview of the studies.

Parthasarathy et al. (2021) investigated the effectiveness of the buying behavior and got the motivation of female buyers towards selected durables in Erode district of the state, India. Independent variables like price, sales place, product attributes, commercial and social influence are taken as driving variables for purchasing attitude and buying motivation for the feminine consumers. This study revealed a powerful effect between customers' attitudes and purchase motivation towards female shopping behavior in the study area.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Question

Whether respondents' demographic details affect the consumer Buying Behaviour in Vaniyambadi Taluk.?

3.2 Research Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between demographic details and Consumer Buying Behaviour.

3.3 Research Design

Empirical Research Design has been adopted in this research work. Primary Data has been collected through circulating well-structured questionnaires among 200 respondents, who hail from different parts of Vaniyambadi Taluk. Secondary Data has been developed by way of Well Reputed Journals, Weekly Magazines, Research

dissertations, Theses, Books, Websites, and So on. The deliberate Sampling Method was adopted all through the research.

4. DATA ANALYSIS & RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A one-Sample t-Test is performed to find differences among five variables of Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour.

One-Sample t-Test is performed to ascertain whether or not significant differences are seen among five variables of Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour such as Problem Diagnosis, Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Evaluation of available alternatives, and selection of product Registering feedback post use. Test Values are taken as 3, with which the mean score is compared. Thereby, the mean difference has been obtained. The following hypothesis is formulated, and validity also is tested with the help of one sample t-Test.

- There exists a significant difference between mean responses of Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour and Test Value of Consumer Buying Behaviour.

Table 4.1: A one-Sample t-Test is performed to find differences among five variables of Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour.

	Test Value = 3					
	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Problem Diagnosis	27.154	199	.000**	1.700	1.58	1.82
Search Engine for relevant information about the product	39.975	199	.000**	.980	.93	1.03
Evaluation of available alternatives	5.761	199	.000**	.270	.18	.36
Selection of Product	-3.577	199	.000**	-.405	-.63	-.18
We are registering Feed Back post use.	11.108	199	.000**	.595	.49	.70

**significant at 5% level

Five variables of Cognitive Buying Behaviour are statistically tested to come up with inference. The five variables regarding Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour include Problem Diagnosis, Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Evaluation of available alternatives, Selection of Product, and Registering feedback post use. P values (significance 2-tailed) in the case of all the five variables are less than the critical alpha value. It indicates highly significant differences among the five variables of Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour. The formulated hypotheses, i.e., “there exists a significant difference between mean responses of five variables of Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour and Test Value of Consumer Buying Behaviour,” are accepted.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis is performed to assess the relationship between a group of observed variables and latent construct of Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour.

To assess the relationship between groups of observed variables, i.e., Problem Diagnosis, Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Evaluation of available alternatives, Selection of Product, and Registering feedback post-use and latent construct, i.e., Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour. Confirmatory Factor Analysis was performed, and the following hypothesis is framed:

- There is a close relationship between groups of observed variables i.e., Problem Diagnosis, Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Evaluation of available alternatives, Selection of Product, and Registering feedback post-use and latent construct, i.e., Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour.

Table 4.2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis concerning Cognitive Consumer Behaviour

(Based on Regression Estimates and Factor Score)

Observed Constructs		Latent Construct	Regression Estimates	Standardized Regression Weights	Factor Score	P
Problem Diagnosis	<---	Cognitive Consumer Behaviour	1.000	.939	-.100	
Search Engine for relevant information about the product			.412	.720	-.058	***
Evaluation of available alternatives			.097	.182	.034	.014
Selection of Product			-.269	-.373	.252	***
Registering feedback post-use			-.646	-.632	.716	***

***significant at .0001 level

From the above table taken up to assess the relationship between observed constructs of Cognitive Consumer Behaviour such as Problem Diagnosis, Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Evaluation of available alternatives, Selection of Product and Registering feedback post-use and latent construct, i.e., Cognitive Consumer Behaviour, Confirmatory Factor Analysis has been performed. Problem recognition is of intercept, and its factor loading is fixed to be 1. This indicates that the scores on the latent variable are some multiple of the selected observed variables. Since p values in three cases such as Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Selection of Product and Registering feedback post-use other than incept (Problem Diagnosis) is less than .0001, the result is significant and formulated hypothesis “observed variables, i.e., Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Selection of Product and Registering feedback post-use and latent construct, i.e., Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour are closely correlated” is accepted. However, “the third observed construct, i.e., Evaluation of available alternatives is not closely correlated with latent construct, i.e., Cognitive Consumer Behaviour as p-value is less than .0001. The result is not significant, and formulated hypothesis, i.e., Evaluation of available alternatives and Cognitive Consumer Behaviour is closely correlated,” is rejected at .0001% level.

5. FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

5.1 Findings

a) In the first finding using single-sample t-test, the five variables regarding Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour include Problem Diagnosis, Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Evaluation of available alternatives, Selection of development, and Posting feedback post use. P values (significance 2-tailed) in the case of all the five variables are less than the critical alpha value. It indicates highly significant differences among the five variables of Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour. The formulated hypotheses, i.e., “there exists a significant difference between mean responses of five variables of Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour and Test Value of Consumer Buying Behaviour,” are accepted.

b) This finding made an to assess the relationship between observed constructs of Cognitive Consumer Behaviour such as Problem Diagnosis, Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Evaluation of available alternatives, Selection of Product and Registering feedback post-use and latent construct, i.e., Cognitive Consumer Behaviour, Confirmatory Factor Analysis has been performed. Problem recognition is of intercept, and its factor loading is fixed to be 1. This indicates that the scores on the latent variable are some multiple of the selected observed variables. Since p values in three cases such as Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Selection of Product and Registering feedback post-use other than incept (Problem Diagnosis) is less than .0001, the result is significant and formulated hypothesis “observed variables, i.e., Search Engine for relevant information about the product, Selection of Product and Registering feedback post-use and latent construct, i.e., Cognitive Consumer Buying Behaviour are closely correlated” is accepted. However, “the third observed construct,

i.e., Evaluation of available alternatives is not closely correlated with latent construct, i.e., Cognitive Consumer Behaviour as p-value is less than .0001. The result is not significant, and formulated hypothesis, i.e., Evaluation of available alternatives and Cognitive Consumer Behaviour is closely correlated,” is rejected at a .0001% level.

5.2 Suggestions

- a) Understanding Consumer Buying Behaviour is vital as it severely impacts an organization's turnover, and the fate of any organization depends on a thorough investigation of Consumer Buying Behaviour. Some organizations fail to delve into figuring out Consumer Buying Behaviour since it increases the day-to-day commercial activities.
- b) Many Organizations focus on research and development of Consumer Buying Behavior, but they fail to cope with what is to be researched on consumer behavior. They conduct the research randomly on target people in some areas but consumers in another territory whose mindsets are not similar to that of the researched areas.
- c) Product should be designed so that consumers' requirements have to be met. Some specifications are not incorporated while developing the product. Therefore, consumers switch over to other branded products.
- d) Consumer Buying Behaviour also depends on the Price of the Air conditioner. They should offer the Air conditioner at the best prices as competition is always prevalent.
- e) Consumer Buying Behaviour depends on word-of-mouth appreciation. Those who buy washing machines will spread the name and fame of the products to their neighbors. This will reflect when consumers have the intention to buy any specific brand of the washing machine. So, manufacturers have to purchase the products by consumer preferences. Similarly, the feedback of consumers should be immediately addressed.

6. CONCLUSION

The study is prominent as figuring out consumer buying behavior is very necessary. Business people in the modern era want to understand their consumers and win their hearts by offering their preferable products. Lack of understanding consumers will lead to the collapse of the business. Consumer buying behavior towards washing machines in Vaniyambadi Taluk will be used to understand other areas' consumers. Business people will also promote sales by fulfilling the needs and requirements of consumers.

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